

THE CONSTITUENTS OF *DIDYMOCARPUS PEDICELLATA*. PART II. COMPARATIVE STUDIES IN THE CONSTITUTION OF PEDICIN, ISOPEDICIN, PEDICININ, AND PEDICELLIN.

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Investigations in the constitution of the colouring matters of *Didymocarpus Pedicellata*, reported in the earlier communication, were carried out chiefly by studying their behaviour towards caustic soda, permanganate, nitric acid and bromine. As a result of these studies they have been established as derivatives of chalcone and benzalcoumaranone. Pedicellin has been shown to be 2:3:4:5:6-pentamethoxychalcone, pedicin to be 5:6-dihydroxy-2:3:4-trimethoxychalcone, pedicinin to be 3:5:6-trihydroxy-4-methoxybenzalcoumaranone and isopedicin to be 5-hydroxy-2:3:4-trimethoxy-benzylcoumaranone. Incidentally it has been brought out that these colouring matters are not allied to duniine as suggested by Robinson in a recent note on the colouring matter of *Streptocarpus Dunii*, Mast.

The preceding communication (Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 12 705) dealt with the isolation and characterisation of the principal colouring matters of *Didymocarpus pedicellata*, namely pedicin, $[C_{18}H_{18}O_6 : -C_{14}H_7(CO)(OH)_2(OMe)_3]$ and the three apparently allied products, isopedicin ($C_{18}H_{18}O_6$), pedicinin $[C_{16}H_{12}O_6 : -C_{15}H_8O_4(OH)(OMe)]$ and pedicellin $[C_{20}H_{22}O_6 : -C_{15}H_7O(OMe)_5]$, the position arrived at in regard to their chemical constitution and mutual relationship being expressed in their simplified formulae above. Their colours and colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid and caustic soda indicate that they do not have a flavone or an isoflavone structure and might be allied to chalcones, while the ferric chloride colour reaction of pedicin suggests that its two hydroxyls are in *ortho*-position.

The present paper embodies the results of subsequent investigations which were principally based on studies in the action of caustic soda, permanganate, nitric acid and bromine. These investigations fairly establish the products under discussion to be derivatives of chalcone and benzalcoumaranone in which the position of the substituents may be indicated as shown in the following tentative structures:

Pedicellin

(2:3:4:5:6-Pentamethoxychalcone),

Pedicin

(5:6-Dihydroxy-2:3:4-trimethoxychalcone).

(III)

Pedicinin

(3 :5 :6-Trihydroxy-4-methoxy-benzalcoumaranone).

(IV)

isopedicin

(5-Hydroxy-2 :3 :4-trimethoxy-benzyl-coumaranone).

Pedicellin is established as a dimethyl ether of pedicin because (a) pedicin is converted to pedicellin on methylation with dimethyl sulphate and the demethoxylation of both these products gives the same pentahydroxy compound which has been named des-pedicellin; (b) the phenylhydrazone of pedicellin indicates the presence in it of a keto group which was already noted in pedicin (Part I, *loc. cit.*); and (c) the formation of dibromo derivatives of pedicellin and dibenzoylpedicin indicate the presence of a single double bond in each one of them. As on heating with caustic soda solution, and also on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide or permanganate, both pedicin and pedicellin yield benzaldehyde, apart from an uncrystallisable acid, which is still under investigation, the presence of a $C_6H_5CH:C<$ grouping in them is considered plausible. These observations simplify the formulae of pedicin and pedicellin to $C_6H(OH)_2(OMe)_3(CO)(C=CH\cdot Ph)$ and $C_6H(OMe)_3(CO)(C=CH\cdot Ph)$ respectively. It is further noted, that the pale yellow isopedicin, which is saturated to bromine, is converted into the unsaturated, orange-red pedicin by caustic soda at the ordinary temperature. This is apparently due to the rupture of a ring. The isomerisation is not due to the enolisation as isopedicin could not be retransformed to pedicin. The relationship between pedicin, isopedicin and pedicellin is thus cleared up.

The relationship of these products to pedicinin is indicated by a series of reactions which simultaneously lead to the elucidation of their constitution. On treatment of pedicellin in glacial acetic acid solution with concentrated nitric acid, it yields a light orange coloured dehydro product, which contains only two methoxyls as against five in pedicinin. This proves to be monomethoxypedicinin, as it undergoes demethylation with dilute alkali at the ordinary temperature and is converted into a product identified as pedicinin. The colour reactions of pedicinin and the fact that benzaldehyde is produced when it is treated with alkali exclude a flavone or isoflavone structure for it. Again, since pedicinin contains the

The above explanation finds further support from the fact that when this desmotropy is guarded against by benzoylating or methylating pedicin, the action of bromine does not result in the formation of dibenzoyl or dimethylpedicin but yields in the normal way dibromodibenzoylpedicin and dibromopedicellin respectively. The presence of a double bond in pedicin is also established by the formation of these two derivatives, as well as by its catalytic reduction with platinum black to a dihydro derivative.

The oxidation of pedicin with permanganate also leads to pedicinin in an apparently analogous manner. Along with the latter, benzaldehyde (characterised by phenylhydrazone, semicarbazone and conversion to benzoic acid) is formed due to hydrolysis of pedicinin.

The demethylation of pedicinin gives a product whose analysis, melting point and mixed melting point show it to be identical with despedicellin. This is obviously due to the rupture of the oxygen ring in the process of demethylation with hydroiodic acid. Despedicellin as obtained from any of the three products (I, II or III) has a pale yellow colour, absorbs bromine in cold, gives a deep red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid, and a dark bluish green colour and smell of benzaldehyde with alkali. With ferric chloride it gives a dark bluish green colouration changing through light orange-red to reddish violet. On the other hand, it gives no characteristic colour of flavones with Mg and HCl. Its constitution as 2:3:4:5 6-pentahydroxychalkone may thus be regarded as fairly established.

The occurrence of pentahydroxybenzene derivatives in nature can not be considered improbable as various authors have in more recent years proved their presence in a number of plant families. Calycopttrin from *Calycopteris Floribunda* (Ratnagiriswaran, Sehra and Venkataraman, *Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 1964) and the identical flavone thapsin from

Digitalis thapsi (Karrer, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1935, I, 715) and also robilitin from *Citrus nobilis* (Tseng and Tseng and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1009) may be given as instances. On the other hand, the occurrence of a number of pentahydroxybenzene derivatives belonging to the chalkone and benzalcumaranone series is of interest. Attempts to synthesise these products are engaging our attention.

Robinson (*Nature*, July, 1938) has recently communicated the isolation of a colouring matter, duniione, $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$, from the deposit on the leaves and inflorescence of *Streptocarpus Dunii*, Mast, and has in view of the close generic relationship of this plant to *Didymocarpus pedicellata* suggested the likelihood of its being related to the colouring matters of the pedicin series. The work embodied in the present paper does not, however, support this suggestion as these products for which a chalkone structure was suggested in the earlier communication have now been definitely established as chalkone and benzalcoumaranone derivatives, while a 2 : 3 : 3-trimethyl-6 : 7-benzocoumarane-4 : 5-quinone or its gem-dimethyl isomeride structure has been suggested for duniione.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methylation of Pedicin : Pedicellin.—To a solution of pedicin (0.4 g.) dissolved in 10 c.c. of 15 % sodium hydroxide solution, dimethyl sulphate (3 c.c.) was slowly added with shaking. The methylated product separated out after some time and on crystallisation from ether yielded colourless stout rods which melted at 98° and gave no depression on admixture with a pure sample of pedicellin, yield 0.35 g. (Found after drying to constant wt. at 50° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 67.09 ; H, 6.14. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 67.03 ; H, 6.13 per cent).

Demethylation of Pedicellin : Des-pedicellin.—Pedicellin (3.5 g.) was refluxed with HI (*d* 1.77, 10 c.c.) for about 4 hours in a metal bath at 130° - 40° . The resultant product was poured into water and the brick red insoluble powder was filtered, washed with water and thio-sulphate solution and dried on a porous plate. The crude demethylated product was successively crystallised from acetone, ethyl acetate and methanol when it finally melted at 255 - 56° (decomp.) with shrinking and partial sublimation at 230° , yield 2.3 g. Despedicellin, thus obtained, formed pale yellow glistening silky needles insoluble in petrol ether, sparingly soluble in ether but fairly soluble in acetone, alcohol or hot ethyl acetate. It is soluble in caustic soda with a dark bluish green colour and begins to decompose in alkaline solution on keeping, giving smell of benzaldehyde. It could not be methylated with dimethyl sulphate

in the usual way. (Found after drying to constant wt. at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 62.5; H, 4.3. $C_{15}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.2 per cent). In alcoholic solution it gives with ferric chloride a deep bluish green colour which fades through light orange-red to reddish violet. On addition of a further drop of ferric chloride it develops a light brownish red colour.

Demethylation of Pedicin and Pedicinin: Despedicellin.—The demethylation products of pedicin, pedicinin and methylpedicinin were obtained in a similar manner as in case of pedicellin and were found to be identical with despedicellin by their m. p. and mixed m. p., formation of similar phenylhydrazones, colour reactions and analyses. [Found after drying demethoxy-pedicin to constant wt. at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 62.6; H, 4.3. Demethoxy-pedicin gave after drying: C, 62.5; 62.2; H, 4.2; 4.3; demethoxy-methylpedicinin gave C, 62.4; H, 4.1. $C_{15}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.2. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 62.9; H, 3.5 per cent).

Despedicellin-phenylhydrazone.—Despedicellin (0.3 g.) was heated in an alcoholic solution with phenylhydrazine (0.2 c.c.) and a drop of acetic acid on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The dark red solution was poured into very dilute acetic acid and the precipitated red sticky mass was washed with water and dissolved in ethyl acetate. On concentration and cooling the solution it yielded long colourless needles of despedicellin-phenylhydrazone, m.p. 196° . (Found after drying to constant wt at 50° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 66.66; H, 5.4. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3, C_8H_8N_2$ requires C, 66.66; H, 4.7 per cent).

The phenylhydrazones of demethylated pedicin, pedicinin and methylpedicinin, prepared in an analogous manner, melted at 196° , 197° and 195° respectively and showed no depression in m.p. on admixture with each other or with despedicellin-phenylhydrazone.

Treatment of Pedicin with Bromine: Pedicinin and Dibromopedicin.—Pedicin (0.1903 g.) was kept with 0.1 g. of bromine (2 atoms) in chloroform solution for a few hours in cold. The bromine was found to be in excess on testing with starch-iodide paper. The solvent was evaporated off under a fan and the residue was dissolved in methanol. On concentration of the methanol solution, carmine red crystalline aggregates of stout rods were obtained, which were free from bromine, melted at 203° and were found to be identical with pedicinin. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 4.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.10 per cent). The mother-liquor on concentration yielded another crop of pedicinin (total 0.07 g., ca 40%). The final filtrate appeared to contain yet another bromine-free product which is under investigation.

On keeping pedicin with 4 equivalents of bromine in the cold, a reddish brown crystalline product was obtained, m.p. 180° (decomp.). (Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : Br, 35.3. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6Br_2$ requires Br, 34.8 per cent).

Bromination of Benzoylpedicin: Dibromodibenzoylpedicin.—Benzoylpedicin (0.1836 g., m.p. 181°) was kept with 0.1054 g. of bromine (equivalent to 4 Br) in chloroform solution in cold for a few hours. The residue obtained after evaporation of the solvent gave 0.14 g. of a dibromo derivative which crystallised from methanol in colourless stout rods, m.p. 170° (decomp.). [Found after drying to constant wt. at 50° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : Br, 22.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6 (C_6H_5CO)_2 Br_2$ requires Br, 22.9 per cent].

Bromination of Pedicellin: Dibromopedicellin.—To a chloroform solution of pedicellin (1 g.) was added a chloroform solution of bromine (equivalent to 2 Br) at the ordinary temperature and the solvent was completely removed on the water-bath. On cooling the petrol ether solution of the residue, the bromo derivative crystallised in rods and needles, m.p. 132° . It was finally crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and ether (in which it is more readily soluble than in petroleum ether) when it came out in bunches and stars of stout rods and needles, yield 1.2 g. (Found in air-dried sample: Br, 30.3. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6Br_2$ requires Br, 30.5 per cent).

Pedicellin-phenylhydrazone.—Pedicellin (0.3 g.) was warmed on a water-bath with phenylhydrazine (0.2 c.c.) with a drop of acetic acid for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The sticky mass, obtained by pouring the solution into very dilute acetic acid, was washed with water, taken up in ethyl acetate, concentrated to a small volume, and cooled, when the phenylhydrazone crystallised out in colourless rods, m.p. $133-35^{\circ}$. (Found after drying to constant wt. at 50° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 69.5; H, 6.30; N, 6.35. $C_{26}H_{28}O_5N_2$ requires C, 69.6; H, 6.25; N, 6.25 per cent).

Action of Nitric Acid on Pedicellin (98°): Methylpedicinin, $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$.—Pedicellin (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (2.5 c.c.) was slowly treated with concentrated nitric acid (d 1.4, 0.5 c.c.) and the solution was immediately diluted with water, when an orange yellow oily product separated out which solidified on cooling. The supernatant liquid was shaken out with ethyl acetate and the solidified product was dissolved in the ethyl acetate extract. The solution was well washed with water, dried with sodium sulphate, concentrated to a small volume and cooled, when a yellowish crystalline mass separated out. Methylpedicinin, thus obtained, melted at 110° , yield 0.52 g. The melting point remained unaltered on crystallisation from alcohol but the colour appeared to be light orange. It is

fairly soluble in ethyl acetate and alcohol, less so in ether and nearly insoluble in petroleum ether. It dissolves in sulphuric acid with a blood red colour which later changes to reddish brown. [Found after drying to constant wt. in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 65.1; H, 4.5; OMe, 18.4. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 65.0; H, 4.4; OMe, 19.8 per cent].

On dissolving methylpedicin in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and acidifying the alkaline solution with dilute hydrochloric acid a dark red product was obtained which on crystallisation from chloroform yielded aggregates of carmine red rods and needles, m.p. 203° . It showed no depression on admixture with a pure sample of pedicin. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0 per cent).

Conversion of isoPedicin to Pedicin.—*isoPedicin* (m.p. 105° , 0.1 g.) was dissolved in 30% sodium hydroxide solution and immediately acidified with hydrochloric acid. On crystallisation of the precipitate from ether pedicin was obtained in orange coloured rectangular plates, m.p. 143° and giving no depression on admixture with pure pedicin.

Oxidation of Pedicin with Potassium Permanganate.—Pedicin (0.43 g.) was dissolved in very dilute sodium hydroxide solution and a 5% solution of potassium permanganate (0.36 g. equivalent to 2O) was slowly added to the alkaline solution with ice cooling. The reaction mixture was separated from the precipitated manganese dioxide and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution yielded an oily residue smelling of benzaldehyde. It was oxidised to benzoic acid, and its phenylhydrazone and semicarbazone which melted at $159-61^\circ$ and 221° respectively showed no depression on admixture with authentic samples.

The alkaline solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate crystallised from chloroform, when it yielded bunches and stars of carmine red rods and needles, m.p. 203° and showed no depression in m.p. on admixture with pedicin. (Found after drying to constant wt. at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 63.8; H, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0 per cent).

Reduction of Pedicin.—Pedicin (1 g.) was shaken with platinum black (0.1 g.) in methyl alcoholic solution for 9 hours during which 70 c.c. of hydrogen were absorbed (required for 1 mol., 65 c.c.). The yellow solution was filtered, freed of the solvent and the oily residue crystallised from ether when it yielded pale yellow hexagonal plates, m.p. $120-21^\circ$, yield 0.8 g. (Found after drying to constant wt. at 50° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 64.7; H, 6.0. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.0 per cent).